

Energy Dispersion Relation of Graphene Beyond the Nearest Neighbor Electron Hopping: A Tight-Binding Approximation Study

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Abstract

In this study, the energy dispersion relation of monolayer graphene using tight-binding approximation was investigated. The study extends beyond the conventional nearest neighbor electron hopping model to capture finer details introduced by interactions of distant atoms. Specifically, contributions from the first, second and third nearest neighbors to achieve a more accurate representation of the band structure were included. The influence of these extended hopping terms on the electronic properties - particularly on the symmetry, bandwidth, and Fermi velocity - is analyzed and discussed. Furthermore, a lattice periodicity axiom that simplifies the inclusion of higher order interactions while preserving the hexagonal symmetry of the graphene lattice was introduced. Results reveal deeper insights into the subtleties of the electronic behavior of graphene and provide a more comprehensive foundation for the future studies involving perturbations, doping or external fields.

Keywords: Energy dispersion, Graphene, Nearest neighbor, Electron hopping, Tight binding, Approximation.

Introduction

Graphene is a two-dimensional (2D) crystal composed of carbon atoms arranged in a hexagonal (honeycomb) lattice. Although it was experimentally isolated in 2004, theoretical investigations into graphene have been ongoing for over 60 years, as it serves as a fundamental structure for understanding the electronic properties of other sp^2 -hybridized carbon allotropes [1,2]. Each carbon atom forms strong σ

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bonds with its three nearest neighbors at 120° angles, resulting from the sp² hybridization of the 2s, 2p_x, and 2p_y orbitals. The fourth valence electron resides in the 2p_z orbital, perpendicular to the graphene plane, and overlaps with adjacent 2p_z orbitals to form π bonds. These delocalized π electrons are crucial in determining graphene's transport properties, and the material's structural flexibility is reflected in its electronic characteristics [3]. The sp² hybridization leads to a trigonal planar structure with carbon–carbon bond lengths of approximately 1.42 Å. The σ bonds contribute to the robustness of the lattice structure, while the π bands, formed by the perpendicular p orbitals, are half-filled due to the Pauli Exclusion Principle [4]. A significant aspect of graphene's energy dispersion is its linear energy-momentum relationship, where the conduction and valence bands intersect at the Dirac points without an energy gap, making graphene a zero band-gap semiconductor with linear long-wavelength energy dispersion for both electrons and holes [5]. Recent studies have highlighted the limitations of the nearest-neighbor tight-binding model in accurately capturing graphene's electronic properties. For instance, Zhang et al. (2023) demonstrated that including interactions beyond the nearest-neighbor approximation is essential for precise calculations of high-order harmonic generation in solids [6]. Similarly, Vidarte and Lewenkopf (2022) analyzed the Landau level spectrum of bulk graphene, incorporating long-range hopping terms to address discrepancies between theoretical predictions and experimental observations [7]. These findings underscore the necessity of considering extended hopping interactions to accurately describe graphene's band structure and related phenomena. Building upon this foundation, the aim is to investigate the effects of first, second, and third nearest-neighbor interactions on graphene's energy dispersion. By systematically including these extended hopping terms, a more comprehensive understanding of their contributions to graphene's electronic properties would be revealed. Additionally, an axiom would be proposed to account for the lattice periodicity, facilitating the incorporation of higher-order interactions while preserving the hexagonal symmetry of the graphene lattice. This approach will offer deeper insights into the subtleties of graphene's electronic behavior and serve as a robust framework for future studies involving perturbations, doping, or external fields.

Research Method

Energy dispersion relation of graphene in its first nearest neighbor electron hopping

The Hamiltonian for arbitrary electron is given by

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \Delta + \sum_{j=1}^N V(r - R_j) \quad (1)$$

In order to derive the band structure of graphene (E-K) relation, the Schrodinger's equation is solved as follows

$$\hat{H}\psi = E\psi \quad (2)$$

The total wave function ψ can be written as a linear combination of two Bloch functions u_A and u_B as follows [8]

$$\psi(\vec{k}, \vec{r}) = C_A u_A(\vec{k}, \vec{r}) + C_B u_B(\vec{k}, \vec{r}) \quad (3)$$

By substituting equation (3) into equation (2), multiplying by the complex conjugate of u_A^* and u_B^* and integrating over the entire space, the Schrodinger's equation in equation (2) can be re-written as follows

$$\begin{pmatrix} E_A - E & \hat{H}_{AB} - ES_{AB} \\ \hat{H}_{BA} - ES_{BA} & E_B - E \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} C_A \\ C_B \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Where S_{AB} and S_{BA} are the overlapping between wave functions of atoms A and B.

To get a non-trivial solution of equation (4), the determinant of the matrix must vanish, therefore

$$E = H_{AA} \pm |H_{AB}| \quad (5)$$

To evaluate the matrix elements which are given in equation (5), the assumptions from the tight binding approximation are used

$$u_{A(B)}(\vec{k}, \vec{r}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{A(B)}^N e^{i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}} A(B) X(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_{A(B)}) \quad (6)$$

where $X(\vec{r})$ is the orbital $2p_z$ wave function for an isolated carbon atom, N is the number of the unit cell [9].

The diagonal matrix elements H_{AA} can be calculated as follows

$$H_{AA} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_i} \int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) \quad (7)$$

Where \vec{R}_i are the vectors connecting atom A to its three nearest neighbour atoms B. Equation (7) becomes

$$H_{AB} = (e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_1} + e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_2} + e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_3}) \int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau \quad (8)$$

Where $\int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau = \gamma_0$ is the transfer integral on the nearest neighbour interaction

$$H_{AB} = (e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_1} + e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_2} + e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{R}_3}) \gamma_0 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{But } \vec{R}_1 = \left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{3}}, 0\right), \quad \vec{R}_2 = \left(\frac{-a}{2\sqrt{3}}, \frac{a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_3 = \left(\frac{-a}{2\sqrt{3}}, \frac{-a}{2}\right)$$

Substituting the coordinates into equation (8) and multiplying the result by its conjugate gives

$$H_{AB} = \gamma_0 \sqrt{1 + 4 \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} k_x a\right) \cos\left(\frac{k_y a}{2}\right) + 4 \cos^2\left(\frac{k_y a}{2}\right)} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, the energy dispersion for the first nearest neighbours in a closed form is

$$E = E_0 \pm |H_{AB}| \quad (11)$$

$$E(k) = E_0 \pm \gamma_0 \sqrt{1 + 4 \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} k_x a\right) \cos\left(\frac{k_y a}{2}\right) + 4 \cos^2\left(\frac{k_y a}{2}\right)} \quad (12)$$

$$E = E_0 \pm \gamma_0 \sqrt{1 + 4 \cos \alpha \cos \beta + 4 \cos^2 \beta} \quad (13)$$

Where $\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} k_x a$ and $\beta = \frac{k_y a}{2}$

Energy dispersion relation of graphene in its second nearest neighbor electron hopping

The atoms in this site are geometrically similar to atom A (the origin atom) and the Hamiltonian is represented by H_{AA}

The diagonal matrix elements (H_{AA}) can be calculated as follows

$$H_{AA} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_A \sum_{A^*} e^{i\vec{k} \cdot (\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}_{A^*})} \int X^*(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_A) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_A) d\tau \quad (14)$$

To calculate the matrix elements in equation (14), six atoms are considered (the next nearest neighbour atoms) in this site

Equation (14) can be re-written as

$$H_{AA} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_i} \int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau \quad (15)$$

$$H_{AA} = (e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_1} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_2} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_3} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_4} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_5} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_6}) \int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau \quad (16)$$

Where $\int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau = \gamma_1$ is the transfer integral on the next nearest neighbour interaction

$$H_{AA} = (e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_1} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_2} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_3} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_4} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_5} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_6}) \gamma_1 \quad (17)$$

The vector coordinates are geometrically calculated as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \vec{R}_1 &= \left(\frac{a\sqrt{3}}{3}, \frac{a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_2 = \left(\frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{-a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_3 = (0, -a), \\ \vec{R}_4 &= \left(\frac{-a\sqrt{3}}{3}, \frac{a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_5 = (0, -a), \quad \vec{R}_6 = \left(\frac{-a\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{-a}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

Substituting the values of all the vectors in equation (18) yields

$$H_{AA} = (e^{-ik_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2}} + e^{ik_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2}}) (e^{-ik_y \frac{a}{2}} + e^{ik_y \frac{a}{2}}) + e^{-ik_y a} + e^{ik_y a} \quad (19)$$

$$H_{AA} = 4 \cos k_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos k_y \frac{a}{2} + 2 \cos k_y a \quad (20)$$

Therefore, the energy band derived from this Hamiltonian for the second nearest neighbor takes the form

$$E(k) = \gamma_1 (4 \cos k_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2} \cos k_y \frac{a}{2} + 2 \cos k_y a) \quad (21)$$

$$E_2(\alpha, \beta) = \gamma_1 (4 \cos \alpha \cos \beta + 2 \cos 2\beta) \quad (22)$$

$$E_2(\alpha, \beta) = \gamma_1 (4 \cos \alpha \cos \beta + 4 \cos^2 \beta - 2) \quad (23)$$

Energy Dispersion of Graphene in its Third Nearest Neighbor Hopping

The atoms in this site are geometrically similar to atoms B (the first nearest neighbour atoms) and the Hamiltonian is represented by H_{AB}

The diagonal matrix elements (H_{AB}) can be calculated as follows

$$H_{AB} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_A \sum_{B^*} e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot (\vec{r}_A - \vec{r}_{B^*})} \int X^*(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_A) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_A) d\tau \quad (24)$$

To calculate the matrix elements in equation (24), the nine atoms are considered (the next nearest neighbour atoms) in this site

$$H_{AB} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_i} \int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau \quad (25)$$

$$H_{AB} = (e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_1} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_2} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_3} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_4} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_5} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_6} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_7} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_8} + e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{R}_9}) \int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau \quad (26)$$

Where $\int X^*(\vec{r}) H X(\vec{r} - \vec{R}_i) d\tau = \gamma_2$ is the transfer integral on the next next nearest neighbour interaction

The connecting vectors are calculated geometrically as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \vec{R}_1 &= \left(\frac{5a\sqrt{3}}{6}, \frac{-a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_2 = \left(\frac{5a\sqrt{3}}{6}, \frac{a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_3 = \left(\frac{a\sqrt{3}}{3}, a\right) \\ \vec{R}_4 &= \left(\frac{-a\sqrt{3}}{6}, \frac{3a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_5 = \left(\frac{-2a\sqrt{3}}{3}, a\right), \quad \vec{R}_6 = \left(\frac{-2a\sqrt{3}}{3}, 0\right) \\ \vec{R}_7 &= \left(\frac{-2a\sqrt{3}}{3}, 0\right), \quad \vec{R}_8 = \left(\frac{-a\sqrt{3}}{6}, \frac{-3a}{2}\right), \quad \vec{R}_9 = \left(\frac{a\sqrt{3}}{3}, a\right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (27)$$

$$H_{AB} = e^{-ik_x \frac{5a\sqrt{3}}{6}} \left(e^{iky \frac{a}{2}} + e^{-iky \frac{a}{2}} \right) + e^{-ik_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{3}} (e^{-iky a} + e^{iky a}) + (e^{iky \frac{3a}{2}} + e^{-iky \frac{3a}{2}}) + e^{ik_x \frac{2a\sqrt{3}}{3}} (e^{-iky a} + e^{iky a}) + e^{-ik_x \frac{2a\sqrt{3}}{3}} \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_{AB} = & 2e^{-ik_x \frac{5a\sqrt{3}}{6}} \cos k_y \frac{a}{2} + 2e^{ik_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{3}} \cos k_y a + 2e^{ik_x \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{6}} \cos k_y \frac{3a}{2} \\
 & + 2e^{ik_x \frac{2a\sqrt{3}}{3}} \cos k_y a + e^{-ik_x \frac{2a\sqrt{3}}{3}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Multiplying by its conjugate H_{AB}^* and simplifying the terms yields the energy dispersion of graphene for the third nearest neighbor electron hopping interms of α and β

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_3(\alpha, \beta) = & E_0 \pm \gamma_2 [1 + 4\cos^2\beta + 4\cos^23\beta + 4\cos2\beta + 8\cos^22\beta + 4\cos\alpha\cos3\beta + 8\cos\alpha\cos3\beta\cos2\beta \\
 & + 4\cos2\alpha\cos2 + 8\cos2\alpha\cos^22\beta + 8\cos\alpha\cos3\beta\cos2\beta + 4\cos3\alpha\cos + 8\cos3\alpha\cos\beta\cos2\beta \\
 & + 8\cos2\alpha\cos\beta\cos3\beta + 8\cos\alpha\cos\beta\cos2\beta]^{\frac{1}{2}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Results and Discussion

Figure 1. The focus on the Dirac points in the dispersion relation which show a conical shape (Generated using Mathematica software) [10]

Figure 2. Band structure of graphene for the second nearest neighbor electron hopping

Equation (12) provides the energy dispersion relation of monolayer graphene within the tight-binding approximation, considering only nearest-neighbor electron hopping. At the Dirac points — specifically at Dirac points, $(\alpha, \beta) = (0, \frac{2\pi}{3}), (\pi, -\frac{\pi}{3}), (-\pi, \frac{\pi}{3})$, the band structure exhibits a linear crossing between the conduction and valence bands. These six points are divided into two inequivalent sets of three, forming the characteristic conical intersections known as Dirac cones. The resulting band structure is half-filled, with the Fermi energy located precisely at the Dirac points, such that the valence band is completely filled and the conduction band remains empty. This behavior is illustrated in Fig. 1 and is a hallmark of graphene's zero-band-gap semiconductor nature. Equation (21) extends the analysis by incorporating second nearest-neighbor hopping into the tight-binding model. The inclusion of these interactions leads to a modification of the band structure, particularly near the Dirac points. At these critical points, the conduction band becomes fully filled while the valence band is pushed further downward in energy, indicating a shift in the Fermi level and an apparent loss of electron-hole symmetry. This alteration in the band topology is depicted in Fig. 2 and highlights the significance of longer-range interactions in accurately modeling graphene's electronic behavior. Lastly, Equation (30) accounts for third nearest-neighbor hopping effects. The corresponding band structure, derived under this extended model, interestingly recovers the linear dispersion at the Dirac points similar to the nearest-neighbor approximation in Equation (12). This implies that third nearest-neighbor interactions reintroduce or preserve the conical nature of the energy bands at these critical points, thereby restoring some aspects of the symmetry that were disrupted by second nearest-neighbor contributions. The resulting band structure remains consistent with the massless Dirac fermion picture, reaffirming the resilience of graphene's unique electronic features even under extended hopping considerations.

Conclusion

In this work, the energy dispersion relations of monolayer graphene have been analyzed by systematically incorporating first, second, and third nearest-neighbor electron hopping within the tight-binding approximation. Our results reveal that both the first and third nearest-neighbor hopping interactions preserve the conical band structure at the Dirac points, where the conduction and valence bands meet linearly. This linear dispersion is a fundamental characteristic of graphene, responsible for its unique electronic behavior, including massless Dirac fermions' dynamics and high electron mobility. Conversely, the inclusion of second nearest-neighbor interactions does not preserve this symmetry. Instead, it results in an overall energy renormalization, leading to the breaking of electron-hole symmetry near the Dirac points without contributing to the formation of new Dirac cones. This indicates that even-order hopping terms, while influencing the finer structure of the bands, do not define the core electronic features of graphene. Based on this observation, it has been concluded that only odd-order nearest-neighbor electron hopping interactions particularly the first and third play a dominant role in determining the low-energy electronic properties of graphene. These odd-order terms are essential for maintaining the symmetry and linearity of the band structure at the Dirac points, whereas even-order contributions serve primarily as perturbative corrections. This understanding provides a refined perspective on the tight-binding modeling of graphene and highlights the selective importance of long-range hopping in accurate electronic structure predictions.

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